

8T – Symmetry of a Universe Packet

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation describing a varying Lorentz manifold, and partitioning it by using functors, we can reach a symmetry among the universe packets and in particular to show that the universe packet is order invariant or commutative.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

We can define a functor:

$$\Lambda : Top \rightarrow Set$$

To switch from a topological space, as manifold wrapping into a discrete setting. Now the entire universe packet is an open set. For simplicity sake we assume it has finite amount of elements, and so it's really a closed set for the sake of the example. The manifold itself is an open manifold due to equation (1) it has no boundary and it is uncompact, the switching into set is than meant to emphasize the object itself, confinement among many others.

$$\emptyset \rightarrow (S_1, S_2 \dots S_K) \tag{1.3}$$

$$S_K = (M_K, g); K \geq 1;$$

$$K \in \mathbb{R};$$

Equation (1.3) meant to specify the closed set of open manifolds, causing the matrix tensor of each manifold to accelerate outward. Notice that there is a symmetry in the set, we can vary each element order it won't make a difference, equation (1) will hold. In particular, the conditions of equation (1.1) will hold either way, and for simplicity we assumed it closed. If there are additional manifold packets joining the set than the conditions of (1.1) could be adiabatically invariant, assuming that is in fact the case we can reach a new prediction:

The rate of acceleration from areas of extremum curvature should increase overtime, if (1.3) is an open set. We can describe the time invariant acceleration as a product of many connected manifolds, assumed stationary which interact at areas of extremum curvature.

$$\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = S_1 \oplus S_2 \oplus \dots S_K \tag{1.4}$$

$$K \rightarrow \infty$$

Equation (1) is another way to represent the idea of universe packet as presented in equation (1.2) and equation (1.21). So this framework curvature is not allowed, in particular for fermions as we proved the term describing them is (1.5) which we insert on equation (1) as an arbitrary variations term.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.5}$$

Curvature is only allowed in primes number or one, that was the construction validating the entire framework, and so led to the mathematical derivation of the coupling constant series, equations (1.6) to (1.9).

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.6}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.7}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.8}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow Set\ of\ Primes$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.81)$$

As bosons were proven discrete amount of net curvature on the metric tensor, we can represent them by the term in equation (1.9):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0; M \rightarrow \infty \quad (1.9)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \in (+1) \cup \mathbb{P}$$

$\mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$

References

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